

Addition of Vermicompost to Soil Influences Total Phenolic Content of Sweet Basil

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Abstract

Sweet basil (*Ocimum basilicum* L.), a medicinal and aromatic plant possessing rich phenolic and terpenoid content, is commonly utilized for culinary and medicinal purposes around the world since ancient times. Vermicompost (VC) products were categorized as biostimulants along with the humic extracts and are utilized for organic fertilizer as well as considered as an organic soil amendment material. Use of organic fertilizers preserves the essential oil yield and natural aroma of basil. In present study, the effect of increasing doses of vermicompost additions (0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40%) on total phenolic content (TPC) in the leaves of sweet basil were investigated. The highest TPC was determined at 10% VC applied group as 90,02 mg/g leaf and the lowest TPC was determined at 30% VC applied group as 50,72 mg/g leaf in dry weight expressed as gallic acid equivalents (GAE). Plant biostimulants are *de novo* products and have proved efficiency in medicinal and aromatic plant cultivation due to their possible inducing activities on the synthesis of secondary metabolites.

Keywords: Basil, Phenolic, Vermicompost,

1. Introduction

Natural compounds from Sweet Basil (*Ocimum basilicum* L.), a well-known member of the Lamiaceae family, have been utilized to flavor foods, in oral care products and as an ornamental herb as well (Simon et al., 1984; Morales and Simon, 1996). Phenolic acid and other aromatic compounds impart basil with antioxidant, antimicrobial and antitumor activities (Gutierrez et al., 2008; Hussain et al., 2008). The application of vermicompost or the other biofertilizers seems to reduce the use of chemical fertilizers and their adverse effects and hence they may play an important role to obtain the purposes of sustainable agriculture (Shokooh et al., 2013).

Organic fertilizer application on basil cultivation preserves the natural aroma and increases the essential oil yield (Hiltunen and Holm, 1999). Vermicompost products were categorized as organic fertilizers by du Jardin (2015) in a regulatory study which was supported and then adopted by relevant EU Commissions. Plant biostimulants are *de novo* products and have proved efficiency in medicinal and aromatic plant cultivation due to their possible inducing activities on the synthesis of secondary metabolites (Raffiet al., 2016).

The aim of this study was to investigate the effects of solid vermicompost application on TPC of basil leaves. Thus, an important contribution to very limited knowledge and prospective researches about the use of organic fertilizers on medicinal and aromatic plant cultivation were aimed as well.

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2. Methodology

Basil seeds were acquired from a farming equipments supplier in Kırşehir/TURKEY. Seeds were sown in 3 seeds per 50 cc containers in a greenhouse in October. At the 3rd week of the germination, one individual in each container was selected and the others were eliminated. The application groups were consisted of 10 basil individuals. Vermicompost applications were carried out by mixing solid vermicompost with soil for the rates of 0%, 10%, 20%, 30%, and 40% to bring final volume of each container to 50 cc.

Figure 1. A view of basil plants at the 3rd week of development.

Upper leaves at similar positions of each individual basil plant were harvested as 15 g, dried at shadow and room temperature, and then subjected to total phenolic content analysis. Total phenolic concentration of the extracts was determined spectrophotometrically according to the Folin-Ciocalteu method (Singleton et al. 1999). Data were analyzed by ANOVA and means were separated by Duncan's Multiple-Range Test at $P < 0,05$. Statistical analysis was performed with SPSS statistic software package (1999).

Figure 2. View of basil plants at the greenhouse

3. Results and Conclusion

3.1 Results

It was determined that the vermicompost addition to soil increased TPC 19% at 10% application group whereas caused a decrease in 33% TPC at 30% application group (Figure 3).

Figure 3. The effects of vermicompost solid applications on total phenolic content of basil.

The results from the rest of the groups, 20% and 40%, were not statistically significant in terms of TPC when compared with control group.

3.2 Conclusion

The existence of humic acid in the content of vermicompost, along with the plant growth hormones auxin and cytokine and their related compounds, were reported as having positive effects on plant growth and development (Scaglia et al., 2016). The results of a recent study (Türkay et al., 2018) which was carried out with solid vermicompost application to the root zone of basil individuals with increasing doses up to 24%, were similar and in concordance with the results of present study (Figure 4).

Figure 4. The effects of vermicompost solid applications on total phenolic content of basil (Türkay et al., 2018).

The results of present study and the study carried out by Türkay et al. (2018) were demonstrated together in Figure 5 with the aim of evaluate the effects of vermicompost addition on TPC in basil leaves precisely.

Figure 5. Comparison of the results of two independent studies aimed to determine the effects of various vermicompost solid application doses on total phenolic content of basil.

According to the results of present study, 10% solid vermicompost addition to soil caused an increase in TPC as 90,03 mg/g leaf and the change was 19% compared to control. This value was consistent with the results of 8% and 12% vermicompost applications in the study previously reported by Türkay et al. (2018). The entire results obtained from present study were substantially in accordance with those relevant results, except a remarkable increase in TPC at the dose of 24% vermicompost application. Vermicomposts acquire very high microbial population as well as having humic acid and plant growth hormones such as auxin and cytokine and their related compounds (Edwards et al., 2011). Besides, it is well known that plant phenolics are defense compounds being incrementally synthesized as a response to the environmental stress conditions both abiotic and biotic (Öztürk & Demir, 2002). The increase in TPC at 24% solid vermicompost application, conceivably was correlated with the higher microbial activity at the root zone of basil individuals.

In present study 30% vermicompost addition to soil resulted with the lowest TPC amount in the basil leaves. Main classes of secondary metabolites, including plant phenolics, are derived from primary metabolites. Therefore, increasing doses of vermicompost application above 24% to the root zone presumably have negative effects on the synthesis of precursor metabolites of phenolic compounds. Although, there was some increase in TPC at the dose of 40% compared to 30% vermicompost application, the higher vermicompost existence above 24% at the root zone of basil individuals caused presumable adverse interactions among the factors of soil.

Vermicomposts and derived products are novel in agronomy and further research is needed for thoroughly evaluate its effectiveness on medicinal and aromatic plant cultivation.

4. References

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